

GARAVISHA: ITS CONTEMPORARY SIGNIFICANCE IN COSMETOLOGY – THE HIDDEN TOXINS IN EVERYDAY LIFE

Dr. Heena Kaushik^{*1}, Dr. Madhusudan Parmar² and Dr. Brijender Singh Tomar³

¹PG Scholar, Final Year, Dept. of *Agada Tantra*, Institute For *Ayurved* Studies and Research, Faculty of *Ayurveda*, Kurukshetra, Haryana, India.

²BAMS, IAS&R, SKAU, Kurukshetra, MHA, DCRUST, Sonipat.

³Professor, Dept. of *Agada Tantra*, Institute for *Ayurved* Studies and Research, Faculty of *Ayurveda*, Kurukshetra, Haryana, India.

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*Corresponding Author

Dr. Heena Kaushik

PG Scholar, Final Year, Dept. of
Agada Tantra, Institute For *Ayurved*
Studies and Research, Faculty of
Ayurveda, Kurukshetra, Haryana,
India.

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ABSTRACT

In *Ayurveda Garavisha* is one of the important concept and is considered as one of the form of *kritrim visha* which gets formed by the combination of two or more that two poisonous and non-poisonous drugs. This results in vitiating all the *Dhatus* that ultimately affects the whole body. The concept of *Garavisha* can be well incorporate with Cosmetic toxicity. *Acarya Susruta* mentions about various *Garavisha Adhishtanas* and its different manifestations. The skin is the main component of one's exterior appearance. Both in the past and the present, external beauty has drawn a great deal of interest and desire. Cosmetics are substances used to enhance the appearance or odour of the human body. The use of cosmetics in the present era has enormously increased and the chemicals like Hydroquinone, Talcum, Parabens, Phthalates, Fragrance, Heavy metals like Lead, Arsenic etc present in them quite frequently cause adverse reactions like contact dermatitis,

allergic hypersensitivity etc. The article is meant to explain the *Garavisha* involvement in day to day activities. The changing life styles, fast food consumption, adulteration in commodities, use of pesticides and other pollutants led people to be exposed to toxins which are the major causative factors for illness. These harmful resources results in exogenous and endogenous toxicities considered as *Garavisha*.

KEYWORDS: *Garavisha*, Cosmetic Toxicity, Heavy Metals, Adulteraion, Ayurveda.

INTRODUCTION

Agada Tantra mentioned *Garavisha* is the type of poison which is prepared artificially by the mixture of various substances. It produces diseases. Since it takes some time for this type of poison to get metabolized and to produce its toxic effects, hence is not immediately fatal.^[1]

Garavisha is the artificial poison (*Kritrima visha*) obtained by combination of parts of the bodies, excreta of different animals, combination of medicines having opposite qualities, ashes and poisonous substances of mild potency.^[2] The word ‘Gara’ comes from ग (Root Word) and अच (Suffix) which means to dilute or in liquid form.^[3] *Garavisha* is prepared artificially by the mixture of various substances and can be administered through different modes like food, drinks, and cosmetics etc; resulting in various diseases. Since it takes long time for this type of poison to get metabolized it doesn’t cause instantaneous death of a person. Incompatible drugs in a formulation and those *Visha yogas* having less potency can also be incorporated into this. Alarming increase in occurrence of various ailments resulted from *Garavisha*. Due to the changing life styles, fast food consumption, adulteration in commodities, use of pesticides and other pollutants, people are exposed to toxins which are the major causative factors for ill health. These harmful resources results in exogenous and endogenous toxicities.^[4]

Around 10000 BC Egyptian were started to use perfumed oils and creams. Around 840 BC Romans and Greeks started to use cosmetics. In present period enormous toxins are accumulated in terrain are taken by the human being itself. Cosmetics are one of them. Nowadays the demand of cosmetic products ranging from skin lightening creams, deodorants, face powder, lotion, shampoo, etc. have increased in recent times, resulting in massive production without following any standard guidelines. Cosmetic Products like, lotion, powder etc is a proven carcinogen linked to ovarian cancer. Imadazolidinyl is a chemical found in hair dyes is also carcinogenic. Synthetic colors and fragrance contain PHTHALATES which interferes immune system. Sodium lauryl sulfate is a compound

commonly seen in face creams for the removal of dirt and oil from skin is proved carcinogenic. Dibutyl phthalate, seen in nail care products is an endocrine disrupter & reproductive toxicant. BHA (butylated hydroxyanisole) and BHT (butylated hydroxytoluene) in lipsticks, moisturisers etc. causes liver, thyroid and kidney problems and affects blood coagulation in experimental animals.^[5]

Garavisha Adhishtanas (source/ mode of poisoning) *Acharya Susruta* mentions about various *Garavisha Adhishtanas*. Some of them have direct link with cosmetic toxicity like *Abyanga Visha* (massage), *Anjana Visha* (eye lid application), *Parisheka Visha* (bath), *Anulepana Visha* (application), *Mukhalepa Visha* (cosmetics) etc. If collyrium is poisonous, it will produce *Daha* (burning sensation), *Vedana* (pain), *Drshiti Vibhrama* (visual difficulties) and *Andhyam* (blindness). *Abyanga Visha* produces symptoms like *Sphota* (eruptions), *Ruja* (pain), *Srava* (exudation), *Twakpaka* (ulcer), *Jwara* (fever), *Mamsanam Daranam* (deep seated ulcers) etc. *Mukhalepa Visha* produces symptoms similar to that of *Abyanga Visha* with additional symptoms like *Syavamukha* (blackish discolouration of the face) and thorny eruptions like those found in the *Padminikantaka* (lotus flower).^[6]

CLASSIFICATION OF COSMETICS: Cosmetics can be broadly classified into 4 categories;

1. Skin care cosmetics - cleansers, toners, moisturizers, creams, lotions, sunscreens etc.
2. Hair care cosmetics - shampoo, conditioners, hair spray, gel etc.
3. Colour/ make up cosmetics - primer, concealer, compact powder, foundation, mascara, eye liner, lip stick, lip liner etc.
4. Fragrance/ perfumes.

MAJOR TOXIC CONTENTS IN THE COSMETICS^{[7],[8],[9]}

CONTENT	PRODUCTS	TOXIC EFFECTS
BHA & BHT	Moisturizers	Endocrine disruption Cancer
DEA-related ingredients	Moisturizers Shampoo	Cancer
Parabens	Body lotions	Endocrine disruption, Breast cancer
Fragrance	Almost all cosmetics	Clogs lymphatic system Endocrine disruption Organ system toxicity
Talc	Eye shadow Blush Baby powder Deodorant Face powder	Lung tumour Ovarian cancer
Formaldehyde	Nail products, Hair dye, Shampoos	Cancer

Phthalates	Fragrance Perfumes Deodorants Lotions	Headaches, Asthma, Dermatitis, Endocrine disruption, Liver/Kidney/ Lung damage, Cancer
Lead	Lipstick Hair dye	Cancer Neurotoxicity
Toluene	Nail polish Hair dye	Reproductive & development al damage Liver and Kidney damage
Oxybenzone	Sunscreen	Contact allergies, photo allergies Endocrine disruption Organ system toxicity
p-phenylenediamine	Hair dye	Skin irritation, Liver toxicity Birth defects Cancer

DISCUSSION

Ayurvedic management of Cosmetic toxicity *Samanya Chikitsa* (general management) of *Garavisha* is mainly *Sodhana* (purifactory therapies) *Vamana* (emesis) and *Virecana* (purgation). Along with this *Hridayavarana* treatment (protection of Heart), administration of *Swarna* (gold), *Samana Prayogas* (palliative treatment) can be utilized.^[10] But in case of cosmetic toxicity, *Samana therapies* (palliative) will be more useful than *Sodhana therapies* (purifactory). The best prevention strategy is to maintain a well regulated life style. A balanced nutritious diet is important in maintaining healthy and beautiful skin. Food with vitamin A, vitamin C, vitamin E, polyphenols etc. should be included in the diet.^[11] Accept yourself and Love the way you look is the important one in the prevention. In *Ayurveda*, there are so many natural methods mentioned which includes single drug therapy and combinational therapy. For example, as cleansers we can use Licorice, *Manjishta* (Indian Madder), Sandal wood, Fenugreek, Lemon peel with water/milk/lemon juice/yoghurt. For scrubbing action - Oats, *Tulasi* (Holy basil), Rose petals with water or barley, Rice bran, *Amalaki* (Gooseberry), *Neem*, *Manjishta* (Indian Madder) with lemon/aloe. As face packs we can use fruits and vegetables with honey/lemon/yogurt according to the skin texture. For normal skin almond oil will be good as moisturizer. Arrow root powder mixed with any *Suganda Dravyas* (aromatic drugs) can be used as face powder. As lip balm butter/*ghee*/*Yashti* (Licorice) + honey or bee wax + butter will be good choice. Traditional *Kajal* preparation with *Sahadevi Moola Swarasa* (juice of *Vernonia cineria*) can replace the toxic eye care cosmetics.^{[12],[13]}

CONCLUSION

Garavisha is an artificial poison explained by *Ayurveda*. In our day to day life we are exposed to such type of toxins. The routine use of cosmetic products is increasingly recognized as a public health, environmental justice, and social justice issue. As per *Ayurveda*

Garavisha shows various types of toxic symptoms & disorders on different systems of the body which mainly includes skin, G.I tract, nervous system, carcinogenic etc. Education and public awareness activities should be conducted to make the people aware of the possible toxins they are exposing through their daily consumables specially cosmetic items and other commodities.

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